

To develop *bona fide* atomistic models of nAChRs in different physiological states, the following initial coordinates from the PDB were used:

- **nAChR $\alpha 7$:**
 - [PDB:7KOO]: nAChR $\alpha 7$ in resting state bound to α -bungarotoxin (chains F-J) and calcium ions
 - [PDB:7KOQ]: nAChR $\alpha 7$ in desensitized state bound to epibatidine (residue name EPJ) and calcium ions
- **nAChR $\alpha 4\beta 2$:**
 - [PDB:6CNJ]: nAChR $\alpha 4\beta 2$ 2 α :3 β stoichiometry in desensitized state bound to nicotine (residue name NCT) and in presence of cholesterol (residue name CHL1) at transmembrane domain
- **nAChR $\alpha 3\beta 4$:**
 - [PDB:6PV8]: nAChR $\alpha 3\beta 4$ in desensitized state bound to AT-1001 (residue name P1M) and in presence of cholesterol (residue name CHL1) at transmembrane domain
- **nAChR muscle-type:**
 - [PDB:6UWZ]: nAChR muscle-type in resting state bound to α -bungarotoxin (chains F and G)

All the structures were processed as follows:

1. Treatment of missing residues:

The structure of nAChR $\alpha 4\beta 2$ contains a portion of unmodeled residues in the intracellular domain. This the loop contains 11 residues for α -subunit and 15 residues for β -subunit. Coordinates for these missing loops were introduced using MODELLER [1]. Out of 10 generated models, the one with the best score according to the MODELLER objective function ($F = 956.0179$) was selected.

The other structures also possess missing loops connecting the intracellular and the transmembrane domains. However, the unmodeled parts exceed 30 residues, which was considered as overly large to be correctly predicted by MODELLER in the absence of a homologous template. The termini of interrupted parts of chains were patched (i.e. amidated at the C-terminus and acetylated at the N-terminus) during the preparation.

2. Protonation of residues:

For all structures, the protonation state of the titratable residues at pH=7 was computed with PROPKA using PDB2PQR tool [2]. The following protonation states were applied:

- nAChR $\alpha 7$ resting state: histidines protonated at N- ϵ except residues 62, 140, 295, 296 and 297 with proton at N- δ
- nAChR $\alpha 7$ desensitized state: histidines protonated at N- ϵ except residues 62, 104, 114, 140, 295, 296 and 297 with proton at N- δ

- nAChR $\alpha 4\beta 2$: at α -subunit histidines protonated at N- ϵ except residues 5, 64, 107, 112, 115, 165 and 301 with proton at N- δ ; at β -subunit histidines protonated at N- ϵ except residues 9, 45, 85, 135, 297, 303, 328 and 329 with proton at N- δ
- nAChR $\alpha 3\beta 4$: at α -subunit histidines protonated at N- ϵ except residues 5, 32, 186, 298 and 305 with proton at N- δ ; at β -subunit histidines protonated at N- ϵ except residues 157, 299, 306 and 318 with proton at N- δ
- nAChR muscle-type: at α -subunit histidines protonated at N- ϵ except residues 3, 24, 25, 27, 104, 204, 299 and 306 with proton at N- δ ; at β -subunit histidines protonated at N- ϵ except residues 105, 112, 160, 305 and 312 with proton at N- δ ; at γ -subunit histidines protonated at N- ϵ except residues 154, 315 and 323 with proton at N- δ ; at δ -subunit histidines protonated at N- ϵ except residues 20, 60, 103, 194, 320, 339 with proton at N- δ and doubly protonated at position 26

3. System preparation:

The molecular systems for MD simulations were prepared using the CHARMM-GUI membrane builder tool [3]. The position of the membrane was predicted using the PPM server [4]. The membrane was modelled to contain 100% 1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (POPC) at both leaflets of the bilayer. The system was solvated in a rectangular box of TIP3P water extending 16Å from the solute edge. NaCl ions were added to ensure charge electroneutrality and mimic the physiological ionic concentration (0.15M). The resulting systems have the following size:

- nAChR $\alpha 7$ resting state – 313 687 atoms
- nAChR $\alpha 7$ desensitized state – 227 272 atoms
- nAChR $\alpha 4\beta 2$ – 199 747 atoms
- nAChR $\alpha 3\beta 4$ – 235 271 atoms
- nAChR muscle-type – 291 942 atoms

4. Molecular Dynamics:

All-atom MD simulations were performed using Gromacs2020 [5]. The systems were simulated in the NPT ensemble at room temperature (300 K) and 1 bar pressure using the CHARMM36m force field [6]. After 5 000 steps of energy minimization and 2.5 ns of equilibration with gradually decreasing restraints (using default restraints provided by CHARMM-GUI), production runs of 100 ns unrestrained MD were carried out with a snapshot saving frequency of 5 ps.

5. Clustering:

Each 10th frame of the trajectory was extracted. Pairwise root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) between all atoms of the protein in each of the selected frames was computed. Frames were then clustered using the single linkage clustering algorithm implemented in Gromacs2020. The RMSD cutoff to assign structures to the same cluster was set to 2.5 Å. The center of the most populated cluster (i.e., the structure with the minimal average pairwise RMSD within the cluster) was extracted and considered as the (statistically) most relevant configuration of the protein in solution.

References:

- [1] A. Fiser, R. K. G. Do, and A. Šali, "Modeling of loops in protein structures," *Protein Sci.*, vol. 9, no. 9, pp. 1753–1773, Jan. 2000, doi: 10.1110/ps.9.9.1753.
- [2] T. J. Dolinsky, J. E. Nielsen, J. A. McCammon, and N. A. Baker, "PDB2PQR: An automated pipeline for the setup of Poisson-Boltzmann electrostatics calculations," *Nucleic Acids Res.*, vol. 32, no. WEB SERVER ISS., Jul. 2004, doi: 10.1093/nar/gkh381.
- [3] J. Lee *et al.*, "CHARMM-GUI Membrane Builder for Complex Biological Membrane Simulations with Glycolipids and Lipoglycans," *J. Chem. Theory Comput.*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 775–786, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1021/ACS.JCTC.8B01066.
- [4] M. A. Lomize, I. D. Pogozheva, H. Joo, H. I. Mosberg, and A. L. Lomize, "OPM database and PPM web server: resources for positioning of proteins in membranes," *Nucleic Acids Res.*, vol. 40, no. D1, pp. D370–D376, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.1093/NAR/GKR703.
- [5] M. J. Abraham *et al.*, "Gromacs: High performance molecular simulations through multi-level parallelism from laptops to supercomputers," *SoftwareX*, vol. 1–2, pp. 19–25, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.softx.2015.06.001.
- [6] J. Huang *et al.*, "CHARMM36m: An improved force field for folded and intrinsically disordered proteins," *Nat. Methods*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 71–73, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1038/nmeth.4067.